

Actual checklist of Tardigrada species (Ver. 13: 01-06-2010)

PETER DEGMA¹ ROBERTO BERTOLANI² ROBERTO GUIDETTI²

¹*Department of Zoology, Comenius University in Bratislava, Mlynská dolina B-1, SK-84215 Bratislava, Slovakia; e-mail: degma@fns.uniba.sk*

²*Department of Biology, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, via campi 213/D, 41100 Modena, Italy; e-mail: roberto.bertolani@unimore.it; roberto.guidetti@unimore.it*

Introduction

More than one thousand Tardigrada species were included in the recently published checklist (Guidetti, R. & Bertolani, R. 2005. Tardigrade taxonomy: an updated check list of the taxa and a list of characters for their identification. *Zootaxa*, 845, 1–46.) plus the additions and corrections to this checklist (Degma, P. & Guidetti, R. 2007. Notes to the current checklist of Tardigrada. *Zootaxa*, 1579, 41–53.). For practical reasons, we have joined these two papers (without comments added to particular taxa as well as without references published in these papers) into an accurate combined version of the checklists. This checklist is free for all users, but utilization of it requires the citation of the two original papers. This paper is the platform for occasional upgrades (date of latest upgrade is in the title). All changes, additions and corrections in comparison with both papers are written in red font. If you also use these changes, please also cite this checklist (web-page instead of journal). Please write us if you find any mistake or missing data in this checklist. Your help in its improvement will be acknowledged.

Acknowledgements

We are very grateful to Professor Clark Beasley (McMurry University, Abilene, U.S.A.) for his suggestions as well as for help with improving the English in the last version of the manuscript. We also thank to Nigel Marley (University of Plymouth, U.K.) for his valuable comments to this checklist.

This study was partly supported by the Slovak Scientific Grant Agency (VEGA) (grant No. 1/3265/06 and 1/0294/09 to PD), by University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (50% FAR) and by Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio di Modena (MoDNA project: Morphology and DNA) to RB and RG.

Checklist of Tardigrada

(The assignment of synonyms are reported within square parenthesis ‘[]’. Amendments are reported within angle brackets ‘< >’. Comments are reported within brace parenthesis ‘{ }’. The species written in bold characters are the genus *type species*)

TARDIGRADA

HETEROTARDIGRADA Marcus, 1927

ARTHROTARDIGRADA Marcus, 1927

Batillipedidae Ramazzotti, 1962
[Discopodidae Marcus, 1934]

Batillipes Richters, 1909

- Batillipes acaudatus* Pollock, 1971
Batillipes adriaticus Grimaldi de Zio, Morone De Lucia, D'Addabbo Gallo & Grimaldi, 1979
Batillipes africanus Morone De Lucia, D'Addabbo Gallo & Grimaldi de Zio, 1988
Batillipes annulatus de Zio, 1962
Batillipes bullacaudatus McGinty & Higgins, 1968
Batillipes carnonensis Fize, 1957
Batillipes crassipes Tchesunov & Mokievsky, 1995
Batillipes dicrocercus Pollock, 1970
Batillipes friaufi Riggin, 1962
Batillipes gilmartini McGinty, 1969
Batillipes lesteri Kristensen & Mackness, 2000
Batillipes littoralis littoralis Renaud-Debyser, 1959
Batillipes littoralis submersus d'Hondt, 1970
Batillipes longispinosus Chang & Rho, 1997
Batillipes marcelli Morone De Lucia, D'Addabbo Gallo & Grimaldi de Zio, 1988
Batillipes mirus Richters, 1909 [*Batillipes caudatus* Hay, 1917]
Batillipes noerrevangi Kristensen, 1978
Batillipes orientalis Chang & Rho, 1997
Batillipes pennaki Marcus, 1946
Batillipes philippinensis Chang & Rho, 1997
Batillipes phreaticus Renaud Debyser, 1959 [*Batillipes littoralis submersus* D'Hondt, 1970]
Batillipes roscoffensis Kristensen, 1978
Batillipes rotundiculus Rho, Min & Chang, 1999
Batillipes similis Schulz, 1955
Batillipes spinicauda Gallo D'Addabbo, Sandulli & de Zio Grimaldi, 2005
Batillipes tridentatus Pollock, 1989
Batillipes tubernatis Pollock, 1971

Coronarctidae Renaud-Mornant, 1974

Coronarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1974

- Coronarctus disparilis* Renaud-Mornant, 1987
Coronarctus fastigatus Renaud-Mornant, 1987
Coronarctus laubieri Renaud-Mornant, 1987
Coronarctus stylisetus Renaud-Mornant, 1987
Coronarctus tenellus Renaud-Mornant, 1974
Coronarctus verrucatus Hansen, 2007

Trogloarctus Villora-Moreno, 1996

- Trogloarctus trionyches*** Villora-Moreno, 1996

Halechiniscidae Thulin, 1928

Archechiniscinae Grimaldi de Zio & D'Addabbo Gallo, 1987
[Archechiniscidae Binda, 1978]

Archechiniscus Schulz, 1953

Archechiniscus marci Schulz, 1953

Archechiniscus minutus Grimaldi de Zio & D'Addabbo Gallo, 1987

Archechiniscus symbalanus Chang & Rho, 1998

Dipodarctinae Pollock, 1995

Dipodarctus Pollock, 1995

Dipodarctus anaholiensis Pollock, 1995

Dipodarctus borrori Pollock, 1995 [*Hemitanarctus chimaera* de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1995/96]

Dipodarctus subterraneus (Renaud-Debyser, 1959)

Euclavarctinae Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Clavarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Clavarctus falculus Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Euclavarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1975

Euclavarctus convergens Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Euclavarctus thieli Renaud-Mornant, 1975

Exoclavarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Exoclavarctus dineti Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Moebjergarctus Bussau, 1992

Moebjergarctus manganis Bussau, 1992

Parmursa Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Parmursa fimbriata Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Parmursa torquata Hansen, 2007

Proclavarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Proclavarctus fragilis Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Florarctinae Renaud-Mornant, 1982

Florarctus Delamare Deboutteville & Renaud-Mornant, 1965

Florarctus acer Renaud-Mornant, 1989

Florarctus antillensis Van der Land, 1968

Florarctus asper Renaud-Mornant, 1989

Florarctus cervinus Renaud-Mornant, 1987

Florarctus cinctus Renaud-Mornant, 1976
Florarctus glareolus Noda, 1987
Florarctus heimi Delamare Deboutteville & Renaud-Mornant, 1965
Florarctus hulingsi Renaud-Mornant, 1976
Florarctus kwoni Chang & Rho, 1997
Florarctus pulcher Grimaldi de Zio, Lamarca, D'addabbo Gallo & Pietanza, 1999
Florarctus salvati Delamare Deboutteville & Renaud-Mornant, 1965
Florarctus stellatus Renaud-Mornant, 1989
Florarctus vulcanius Renaud-Mornant, 1987

Ligiarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1982

Ligiarctus eastwardi Renaud-Mornant, 1982

Wingstrandarctus Kristensen, 1984

Wingstrandarctus corallinus Kristensen, 1984

Wingstrandarctus crypticus Renaud-Mornant, 1989

Wingstrandarctus intermedius (Renaud-Mornant, 1967)

Halechiniscinae (Thulin, 1928)

Chrysoarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Chrysoarctus briandi Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Chrysoarctus flabellatus (Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia, Vaccarella & Grimaldi, 1982)

Halechiniscus Richters, 1908

Halechiniscus chafarinensis Grimaldi de Zio & Villora Moreno, 1995

Halechiniscus greveni Renaud-Mornant & Deroux, 1976

Halechiniscus guteli Richters, 1908

Halechiniscus jejuensis Chang & Rho, 2002

Halechiniscus macrocephalus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1988

Halechiniscus paratuleari Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1988

Halechiniscus perfectus Schulz, 1955

Halechiniscus remanei remanei Schulz, 1955

Halechiniscus remanei antillensis Renaud-Mornant, 1985

Halechiniscus tuleari Renaud-Mornant, 1979

Paradoxipus Kristensen & Higgins, 1989

Paradoxipus orzeliscoides Kristensen & Higgins, 1989

Orzeliscinae (Schulz, 1963)

Orzeliscus du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1952

Orzeliscus belopus du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1952

Orzeliscus septentrionalis Schulz, 1953

Opydorscus Renaud-Mornant, 1989

Opydorscus fonsecae Renaud-Mornant, 1989

Styraconyxinae Kristensen & Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Angursa Pollock, 1979

Angursa antarctica Villora-Moreno, 1998

Angursa bicuspis bicuspis Pollock, 1979

Angursa bicuspis clavifera Noda, 1985

Angursa bicuspis abyssalis Renaud-Mornant, 1981

Angursa capsula Bussau, 1992

Angursa lanceolata Renaud-Mornant, 1981

Angursa lingua Bussau, 1992

Bathyechiniscus Steiner, 1926

Bathyechiniscus tetronyx Steiner, 1926

Lepoarctus Kristensen & Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Lepoarctus coniferus (Renaud-Mornant, 1975)

Paratanarctus D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1992

Paratanarctus kristenseni D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1992

Pleocola Cantacuzène, 1951

Pleocola limnoriae Cantacuzène, 1951

Raiarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1981

Raiarctus aureolatus Renaud-Mornant, 1981

Raiarctus colurus Renaud-Mornant, 1981

Raiarctus variabilis D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio & Morone De Lucia, 1986

Rhomboarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Rhomboarctus aslaki Hansen, Gallo D'Addabbo & de Zio Grimaldi, 2003

Rhomboarctus duplicicaudatus Hansen, Gallo D'Addabbo & de Zio Grimaldi, 2003

Rhomboarctus thomassini Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Styraconyx Thulin, 1942

Styraconyx craticuliformis Chang & Rho, 1998

Styraconyx craticulus (Pollock, 1983)

Styraconyx hallasi Kristensen, 1977

Styraconyx haploceros Thulin, 1942

Styraconyx kristenseni kristenseni Renaud-Mornant, 1981

Styraconyx kristenseni neocaledonensis Renaud-Mornant, 1981

Styraconyx nanoqsunguak Kristensen & Higgins, 1984

Styraconyx paulae Robotti, 1971

Styraconyx qivitoq Kristensen & Higgins, 1984

Styraconyx sardiniae D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Grimaldi de Zio, 1989

Styraconyx sargassi Thulin, 1942
Styraconyx testudo D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio & Morone De Lucia, 1984
Styraconyx tyrrhenus D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Grimaldi de Zio, 1989

Tetrakentron Cuénot, 1892

Tetrakentron synaptae Cuénot, 1892

Tholoarctus Kristensen & Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Tholoarctus natans natans Kristensen & Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Tholoarctus natans pedunculatus D'Addabbo Gallo, de Zio Grimaldi, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1992

Tanarctinae Renaud-Mornant, 1980

Actinarctus Schulz, 1935

Actinarctus doryphorus doryphorus Schulz, 1935

Actinarctus doryphorus ocellatus Renaud-Mornant, 1971

Actinarctus lyrophorus Renaud-Mornant, 1979

Actinarctus neretinus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia, Vaccarella & Grimaldi, 1982

Actinarctus physophorus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia, Vaccarella & Grimaldi, 1982

Tanarctus Renaud-Debyser, 1959

Tanarctus arborspinosus Lindgren, 1971

Tanarctus bubulubus Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2001

Tanarctus dendriticus Renaud-Mornant, 1980

Tanarctus gracilis Renaud-Mornant, 1980

Tanarctus helleouetae Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Tanarctus heterodactylus Renaud-Mornant, 1980

Tanarctus longisetosus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia, Vaccarella & Grimaldi, 1982

Tanarctus minotauricus Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Tanarctus ramazzottii Renaud-Mornant, 1975

Tanarctus tauricus Renaud-Debyser, 1959

Tanarctus velatus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976

Zioella Renaud-Mornant, 1987

Zioella pavonina Renaud-Mornant, 1987

Neoarctidae (de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1992)

Neoarctus de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1992

Neoarctus primigenius de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1992

Neostygarctidae de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo & De Lucia Morone, 1987

Neostygarctus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1982
Neostygarctus acanthophorus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1982

Renaudarctidae Kristensen & Higgins, 1984

Renaudarctus Kristensen & Higgins, 1984
Renaudarctus psammocryptus Kristensen & Higgins, 1984

Stygarctidae Schulz, 1951

Megastygarctidinae Bello & de Zio Grimaldi, 1998

Megastygarctides McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976
Megastygarctides christinae Hansen & Kristensen, 2006
Megastygarctides gerdae Hansen & Kristensen, 2006
Megastygarctides isounguis Renaud-Mornant, 1981
Megastygarctides orbiculatus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976
Megastygarctides setoloso Morgan & O'Reilly, 1988

Stygarctinae Schulz, 1951

Parastygarctus Renaud-Debyser, 1965
Parastygarctus biungulatus Morone De Lucia, Grimaldi de Zio & D'Addabbo Gallo, 1984
Parastygarctus higginsi Renaud-Debyser, 1965
Parastygarctus mediterranicus Gallo D'Addabbo, Grimaldi de Zio & Sandulli, 2001
Parastygarctus renaudae Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Daddabbo, 1987
Parastygarctus sterreri Renaud-Mornant, 1970

Pseudostygarctus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976
Pseudostygarctus apuliae Gallo D'Addabbo, de Zio Grimaldi & D'Addabbo, 2000
Pseudostygarctus intermedius (Renaud-Mornant, 1979)
Pseudostygarctus mirabilis de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1998
Pseudostygarctus rugosus Gallo D'Addabbo, de Zio Grimaldi & Sandulli, 2001
Pseudostygarctus triungulatus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976

Stygarctus Schulz, 1951

Stygarctus abornatus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976
Stygarctus bradypus Schulz, 1951
Stygarctus goubaultae Renaud-Mornant, 1981
Stygarctus granulatus Pollock, 1970
Stygarctus lambertii Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Daddabbo, 1987
Stygarctus spinifer Hiruta, 1985

ECHINISCOIDEA Richters, 1926

Echiniscoididae Kristensen & Hallas, 1980

Anisonyches Pollock, 1975

Anisonyches deliquus Chang & Rho, 1998

Anisonyches diakidius Pollock, 1975

Anisonyches mauritanus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Daddabbo, 1987

Echiniscoides Plate, 1888

Echiniscoides andamanensis Chang & Rho, 1998

Echiniscoides bruni D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1992

Echiniscoides higginsi Hallas & Kristensen, 1982

Echiniscoides hoepneri Kristensen & Hallas, 1980

Echiniscoides horningi Miller & Kristensen, 1999

Echiniscoides pollocki Hallas & Kristensen, 1982

Echiniscoides sigismundi sigismundi (M. Schultze, 1865)

Echiniscoides sigismundi galliensis Kristensen & Hallas, 1980

Echiniscoides sigismundi groenlandicus Kristensen & Hallas, 1980

Echiniscoides sigismundi hispaniensis Kristensen & Hallas, 1980

Echiniscoides sigismundi mediterranicus Kristensen & Hallas, 1980

Echiniscoides sigismundi polynesiensis Renaud-Mornant, 1976

Echiniscoides sigismundi porphyrae Grimaldi de Zio, Gallo D'Addabbo & Pietanza, 2000

Echiniscoides sigismundi verrucariae Grimaldi de Zio, Gallo D'Addabbo & Pietanza, 2000

Echiniscoides travei Bellido & Bertrand, 1981

Carphaniidae Binda & Kristensen, 1986

Carphania Binda, 1978

Carphania fluviatilis Binda, 1978

Oreellidae Puglia, 1959

Oreella Murray, 1910

Oreella mollis Murray, 1910 [*Oreella minor* Ramazzotti, 1964]

Oreella vilucensis Rahm, 1931 *species inquidenda* [*Oreella bonnensis* Rahm, 1932]

Echiniscidae Thulin, 1928

Antechiniscus Kristensen, 1987

Antechiniscus conversus (Horning & Schuster, 1983)

Antechiniscus jermani Rossi & Claps, 1989

Antechiniscus lateromamillatus (Ramazzotti, 1964)

Antechiniscus moscali Claxton, 2001

Antechiniscus parvisentus (Horning & Schuster, 1983)

Antechiniscus perplexus (Horning & Schuster, 1983)

Bryochoerus Marcus, 1936

Bryochoerus intermedius intermedius (Murray, 1910)

Bryochoerus intermedius hawaiiicus (Thulin, 1928)
Bryochoerus intermedius laevis (Marcus, 1936)

Bryodelphax Thulin, 1928

Bryodelphax aaseae Kristensen, Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2010

Bryodelphax alzirae (du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944)

Bryodelphax amphoterus (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975)

Bryodelphax asiaticus Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004

Bryodelphax atlantis Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2008

Bryodelphax brevidentatus Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Degma, 2005

Bryodelphax crossotus Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983

Bryodelphax dominicanus (Schuster & Toftner, 1982)

Bryodelphax iohannis Bertolani, Guidi & Rebecchi, 1996

Bryodelphax lijiangensis Yang, 2002

Bryodelphax mateusi (Fontoura, 1982)

Bryodelphax ortholineatus (Bartoš, 1963)

Bryodelphax parvulus Thulin, 1928

Bryodelphax sinensis (Pilato, 1974)

Bryodelphax tatrensis (Węglarska, 1959)

Bryodelphax weglarskae (Pilato, 1972)

Cornechiniscus Maucci & Ramazzotti, 1981

Cornechiniscus brachycornutus Maucci, 1987

Cornechiniscus ceratophorus (Maucci, 1973)

Cornechiniscus cornutus (Richters, 1906) [*Pseudechiniscus intermedius* Mihelčič, 1970]

Cornechiniscus holmeni (Petersen, 1951)

Cornechiniscus lobatus (Ramazzotti, 1943) [*Pseudechiniscus cornutus* Mihelčič, 1966]

Cornechiniscus madagascariensis Maucci, 1993

Cornechiniscus schrammi (Dastych, 1979)

Cornechiniscus subcornutus Maucci & Ramazzotti, 1981

Cornechiniscus tibetanus (Maucci, 1979)

Echiniscus C.A.S. Schultze, 1840

Echiniscus africanus Murray, 1907

Echiniscus aliquantillus Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983

Echiniscus angolensis da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1964

Echiniscus apuanus M. Bertolani, 1946

Echiniscus arcangelii Maucci, 1973-74

Echiniscus arctomys Ehrenberg, 1853

Echiniscus arthuri Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2005

Echiniscus azoricus Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2008

Echiniscus baius Marcus, 1928

Echiniscus baloghi Iharos, 1973

Echiniscus barbarae Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2002

Echiniscus batramiae Iharos, 1936

Echiniscus becki Schuster & Grigarick, 1966

Echiniscus bigranulatus Richters, 1907

Echiniscus bisculptus Maucci, 1983
Echiniscus blumi blumi Richters, 1903 [*Echiniscus ramazzottii* Binda & Pilato, 1969]
Echiniscus blumi schizofilus Bartoš, 1941
Echiniscus calcaratus Richters, 1908
Echiniscus calvus Marcus, 1931
Echiniscus canadensis Murray, 1910 [*Echiniscus punctulatus* Mihelčič, 1955; *Echiniscus bellus* Mihelčič, 1967]
Echiniscus canedoi da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1962
Echiniscus capillatus Ramazzotti, 1956
Echiniscus carsicus Mihelčič, 1966
Echiniscus carusoi Pilato, 1972
Echiniscus cavagnaroi Schuster & Grigarick, 1966
Echiniscus cervicornis Murray, 1906
Echiniscus charrua Claps & Rossi, 1997
Echiniscus cheonyoungi Moon & Kim, 1994
Echiniscus cirinoi Binda & Pilato, 1993
Echiniscus clevelandi Beasley, 1999
Echiniscus columinis Murray, 1911
Echiniscus corrugicaudatus McInnes, 2009
Echiniscus crassispinosus crassispinosus Murray, 1907
Echiniscus crassispinosus fasciatus Marcus, 1928
Echiniscus curiosus Claxton, 1996
Echiniscus darienae Miller, Horning & Dastych, 1995
Echiniscus dearmatus Bartoš, 1935 [*Echiniscus szaboi* Iharos, 1973]
Echiniscus dikenli Maucci, 1973
Echiniscus diploglyptus Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975
Echiniscus divergens Marcus, 1936
Echiniscus dreyfusi de Barros, 1942
Echiniscus duboisi Richters, 1902
Echiniscus egnatiae Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1979
Echiniscus ehrenbergi Dastych & Kristensen, 1995
Echiniscus elaeinae Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2005
Echiniscus elegans Richters, 1906
Echiniscus evelinae de Barros, 1942
Echiniscus filamentosus Plate, 1888
Echiniscus ganzareki Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2007
Echiniscus glaber Bartoš, 1937
Echiniscus granulatus (Doyère, 1840) [*Echiniscus crassus* Richters, 1904; *Echiniscus fortis* Bartoš, 1935; *Echiniscus abanti* Maucci, 1973]
Echiniscus heterospinosus Maucci, 1954
Echiniscus hexacanthus Maucci, 1973
Echiniscus hoonsooi Moon & Kim, 1990
Echiniscus horningi Schuster & Grigarick, 1971
Echiniscus inocelatus Mihelčič, 1938 [*Echiniscus inocellatus* Mihelčič, 1964]
Echiniscus insuetus Mihelčič, 1967
Echiniscus jagodici Mihelčič, 1951
Echiniscus jamesi Claxton, 1996

Echiniscus japonicus Morikawa, 1951
Echiniscus jenningsi Dastych, 1984
Echiniscus kerguelensis Richters, 1904
Echiniscus knowltoni Schuster & Grigarick, 1971
Echiniscus kofordi Schuster & Grigarick, 1966
Echiniscus lapponicus Thulin, 1911
Echiniscus laterosetosus Ito, 1993
Echiniscus laterospinosus Rudescu, 1964
Echiniscus latifasciatus Dudichev & Biserov, 2000
Echiniscus lichenorum Maucci, 1983
Echiniscus limai da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1964
Echiniscus lineatus Pilato, Fontoura, Lisi & Beasley, 2008
Echiniscus longispinosus Murray, 1907
Echiniscus loxophthalmus Richters, 1911
Echiniscus madonnae Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2006
Echiniscus maesi Séméria, 1985
Echiniscus malpighii Biserov, 1994
Echiniscus manuelae da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1962
Echiniscus marculsi Pilato, Claxton & Binda, 1989
Echiniscus marginatus Binda & Pilato, 1994
Echiniscus marginoporus Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983
Echiniscus markezi Mihelčič, 1971/72
Echiniscus marleyi X. Li, 2007
Echiniscus mauccii Ramazzotti, 1956
Echiniscus mediantus Marcus, 1930
Echiniscus merokensis merokensis Richters, 1904 [*Echiniscus iharosi* Rudescu, 1964]
Echiniscus merokensis suecicus Thulin, 1911
Echiniscus migiurtinus Franceschi, 1957
Echiniscus mihelcici Iharos, 1973
Echiniscus militaris Murray, 1911
Echiniscus molluscorum Fox & Garcia-Moll, 1962
Echiniscus moniliatus Iharos, 1967
Echiniscus montanus Iharos, 1982
Echiniscus mosaicus Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983
Echiniscus multispinosus da Cunha, 1944
Echiniscus murrayi Iharos, 1969
Echiniscus nelsonae X. Li, L. Wang & Yu, 2007
Echiniscus nepalensis Dastych, 1975
Echiniscus nigripustulus Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978
Echiniscus nobilis Mihelčič, 1967
Echiniscus oihonnae Richters, 1903
Echiniscus ollantaytamboensis Nickel, Miller & Marley, 2001
Echiniscus osellai Maucci, 1975
Echiniscus pajstunensis Bartoš, 1941
Echiniscus palmai Dastych, 1997
Echiniscus perarmatus Murray, 1907
Echiniscus peruvianus Binda & Pilato, 1994

Echiniscus perviridis Ramazzotti, 1959
Echiniscus phocae du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944
Echiniscus polygonalis Ito, 1993
Echiniscus poeensis Rodriguez-Roda, 1948
Echiniscus porabrus Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978
Echiniscus postojnensis Mihelčič, 1967 [*Echiniscus loxophthalmus* Mihelčič, 1939]
Echiniscus pseudelegans Séméria, 1994
Echiniscus pseudowendti Dastych, 1984
Echiniscus punctus McInnes, 1995
Echiniscus pusae Marcus, 1928
Echiniscus quadrispinosus quadrispinosus Richters, 1902 [*Echiniscus scrofa* Richters, 1902]
Echiniscus quadrispinosus brachyspinosus Bartoš, 1934
Echiniscus quadrispinosus cribrosus Murray, 1907
Echiniscus quadrispinosus fissispinosus Murray, 1907
Echiniscus quitensis Pilato, 2007
Echiniscus rackae Dastych, 1986
Echiniscus ranzii Ramazzotti, 1964
Echiniscus reticulatus Murray, 1905
Echiniscus reymondi Marcus, 1928
Echiniscus robertsi Schuster & Grigarick, 1965
Echiniscus rodnae Claxton, 1996
Echiniscus rufoviridis du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944
Echiniscus rugospinosus Marcus, 1928
Echiniscus scabrospinosus Fontoura, 1982 <Amended by Pilato *et al.* 2008b>
Echiniscus semifoveolatus Ito, 1993
Echiniscus shaanxiensis X. Li, L. Wang & Yu, 2007
Echiniscus siegristi Heinis, 1911
Echiniscus simba Marcus, 1928
Echiniscus speciosus Mihelčič, 1967 [*Echiniscus roseus* Mihelčič, 1967]
Echiniscus spiculifer Schaudinn, 1901
Echiniscus spiniger Richters, 1904
Echiniscus spinulosus (Doyère, 1840)
Echiniscus storkani Bartoš, 1940
Echiniscus sylvanus Murray, 1910
Echiniscus taibaiensis L. Wang & X. Li, 2005
Echiniscus tamus Mehlen, 1969 <Amended by Miller & Mehlen 2007>
Echiniscus tardus Mihelčič, 1951
Echiniscus tenuis Marcus, 1928
Echiniscus tessellatus Murray, 1910
Echiniscus testudo (Doyère, 1840) [*Echiniscus bellermani* C.A.S. Schultze, 1840; *Echiniscus inermis* Richters, 1902; *Echiniscus trifilis* Rahm, 1921; *Echiniscus filamentosus mongoliensis* Iharos, 1973]
Echiniscus trisetosus Cuénot, 1932
Echiniscus trojanus Maucci, 1973
Echiniscus tropicalis Binda & Pilato, 1995
Echiniscus tympanista Murray, 1911
Echiniscus velaminis Murray, 1910

Echiniscus vinculus Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978
Echiniscus virginicus Riggin, 1962 <Amended by Christenberry & Mason 1979>
Echiniscus viridianus Pilato, Fontoura & Lisi, 2007
Echiniscus viridis Murray, 1910 <Amended by Pilato *et al.* 2008a>
Echiniscus viridissimus Péterfi, 1956
Echiniscus walteri Pilato & Lisi, 2003
Echiniscus weisseri Maucci, 1978
Echiniscus wendti Richters, 1903
Echiniscus zetotrymus Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978

Hypechiniscus Thulin, 1928

Hypechiniscus exarmatus (Murray, 1907) [*Oreella breviclava* Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983]
Hypechiniscus gladiator gladiator (Murray, 1905) [*Parechiniscus unispinosus* da Cunha, 1947]
Hypechiniscus gladiator bigladii (Iharos, 1973)
Hypechiniscus gladiator fissigladii (Iharos, 1973)
Hypechiniscus gladiator spinulosa (Iharos, 1973)
Hypechiniscus papillifer Robotti, 1972

Mopsechiniscus du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944

Mopsechiniscus frenoti Dastych, 1999
Mopsechiniscus granulosus Mihelčič, 1967
Mopsechiniscus imberbis (Richters, 1907)
Mopsechiniscus schusteri Dastych, 1999
Mopsechiniscus tasmanicus Dastych & Moscal, 1992

Novechiniscus Kristensen, 1987

Novechiniscus armadilloides (R.O. Schuster, 1975)

Parechiniscus Cuénot, 1926

Parechiniscus chitonides Cuénot, 1926
Parechiniscus unispinosus da Cunha, 1947

Proechiniscus Kristensen, 1987

Proechiniscus hanneae (Petersen, 1951)

Pseudechiniscus Thulin, 1911

Pseudechiniscus alberti Dastych, 1987
Pseudechiniscus asper Abe, Utsugi & Takeda, 1998
Pseudechiniscus bartkei Węglarska, 1962
Pseudechiniscus beasleyi X. Li, L. Wang & Yu, 2007
Pseudechiniscus bidenticulatus Bartoš, 1963
Pseudechiniscus bispinosus (Murray, 1907)
Pseudechiniscus brevimontanus Kendall-Fite & Nelson, 1996
Pseudechiniscus clavatus Mihelčič, 1955
Pseudechiniscus conifer (Richters, 1904)
Pseudechiniscus dicrani Mihelčič, 1938

Pseudechiniscus distinctus Mihelčič, 1951
Pseudechiniscus facettalis Petersen, 1951 [*Pseudechiniscus pseudoconifer facettalis* Maucci, 1954]
Pseudechiniscus goedeni Grigarick, Mihelčič & Schuster, 1964
Pseudechiniscus gullii Pilato & Lisi, 2006
Pseudechiniscus insolitus Maucci, 1991
Pseudechiniscus islandicus (Richters, 1904)
Pseudechiniscus jiroveci Bartoš, 1963
Pseudechiniscus juanita de Barros, 1939 [*Pseudechiniscus suillus franciscae* de Barros, 1942]
Pseudechiniscus jubatus Biserov, 1990
Pseudechiniscus megacephalus Mihelčič, 1951
Pseudechiniscus nataliae Biserov & Maucci, 1986
Pseudechiniscus novaezeelandiae novaezeelandiae (Richters, 1908)
Pseudechiniscus novaezeelandiae aspinosa Iharos, 1963
Pseudechiniscus novaezeelandiae laterospinosa Iharos, 1963
Pseudechiniscus novaezeelandiae marinae Bartoš, 1934
Pseudechiniscus occultus Dastyh, 1980
Pseudechiniscus papillosus X. Li, L. Wang, Liu & Su, 2005
Pseudechiniscus pilato X. Li, 2007
Pseudechiniscus pseudoconifer Ramazzotti, 1943
Pseudechiniscus pulcher (Murray, 1910)
Pseudechiniscus quadrilobatus Iharos, 1969
Pseudechiniscus ramazzottii ramazzottii Maucci, 1952
Pseudechiniscus ramazzottii facettalis Iharos, 1964 [*Pseudechiniscus ramazzottii lineatus* Maucci, 1973-74]
Pseudechiniscus raneyi Grigarick, Mihelčič & Schuster, 1964
Pseudechiniscus scortecii Franceschi, 1952
Pseudechiniscus shilinensis Yang, 2002
Pseudechiniscus sinensis Rahm, 1937
Pseudechiniscus spinerectus Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2001
Pseudechiniscus suillus (Ehrenberg, 1853) [*Echiniscus mutabilis* Murray, 1905]
Pseudechiniscus transsylvanicus Iharos, 1936
Pseudechiniscus victor (Ehrenberg, 1853) [*Pseudechiniscus tridentifer* Bartoš, 1935]
Pseudechiniscus yunnanensis L. Wang, 2009

Testechiniscus Kristensen, 1987

Testechiniscus laterculus (Schuster, Grigarick & Toftner, 1980)
Testechiniscus macronyx (Richters, 1907)
Testechiniscus meridionalis (Murray, 1906)
Testechiniscus spitsbergensis (Scourfield, 1897) [*Echiniscus clavisetosus* Mihelčič, 1958; *Echiniscus marinellae* Bartoš, 1935; *Echiniscus melanophthalmus* Bartoš, 1936; *Echiniscus menzeli* Heinis, 1917; *Echiniscus rosaliae* Mihelčič, 1951; *Echiniscus spinuloides* Murray, 1907]

MESOTARDIGRADA Rahm, 1937

THERMOZODIA Ramazzotti & Maucci, 1983

Thermozodiidae Rahm, 1937

Thermozodium Rahm, 1937

Thermozodium esakii Rahm, 1937

EUTARDIGRADA Richters 1926

APOCHELA Schuster, Nelson, Grigarick & Christenberry, 1980

Milnesiidae Ramazzotti, 1962

Limmenius Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978

Limmenius porcellus Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978

Milnesioides Claxton, 1999

Milnesioides exsertum Claxton, 1999

Milnesium Doyère, 1840

Milnesium alabamae Wallendorf & Miller, 2009

Milnesium almatyense Tumanov, 2006

Milnesium antarcticum Tumanov, 2006

Milnesium asiaticum Tumanov, 2006

Milnesium brachyungue Binda & Pilato, 1990

Milnesium dujianensis Yang, 2003

Milnesium eurystomum Maucci, 1991

Milnesium katarzynae Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Beasley, 2004

Milnesium krzysztofi Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2007

Milnesium longiungue Tumanov, 2006

Milnesium reductum Tumanov, 2006

Milnesium reticulatum Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2002

Milnesium swolenskyi Bertolani & Grimaldi, 2000 {fossil species}

Milnesium tardigradum tardigradum Doyère, 1840

Milnesium tardigradum granulatum Ramazzotti, 1962

Milnesium tardigradum trispinosa Rahm, 1931

Milnesium tetralamellatum Pilato & Binda, 1991

PARACHELA Schuster, Nelson Grigarick & Christenberry, 1980

Beornidae Cooper, 1964

Beorn leggi Cooper, 1964 {fossil species}

Eohypsibiidae Bertolani & Kristensen, 1987

[*Amphibolus* R. Bertolani, 1981]

Bertolanus Özdikmen, 2008

[*Amphibolus* R. Bertolani, 1981 in Özdikmen 2008]

Bertolanius mahunkai (Iharos, 1971)
Bertolanius markevichi (Biserov, 1992)
Bertolanius nebulosus (Dastych, 1983)
Bertolanius portucalensis Fontoura, Pilato, Lisi & Morais, 2009
Bertolanius smreczynskii (Węglarska, 1970)
Bertolanius volubilis (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975)
Bertolanius weglarskae (Dastych, 1972)

Eohypsibius Kristensen, 1982

Eohypsibius nadjae Kristensen, 1982

Eohypsibius terrestris Ito, 1988

Calohypsibiidae Pilato, 1969

Calohypsibius Thulin, 1928

Calohypsibius ornatus (Richters, 1900) [*Hypsibius* (*Calohypsibius*) *armatus* Bartoš, 1938;

Hypsibius (*Calohypsibius*) *intermedius* Mihelčič, 1939]

Calohypsibius maliki Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2005

Calohypsibius placophorus (da Cunha, 1943)

Calohypsibius schusteri Nelson & McGlothlin, 1996

Calohypsibius verrucosus (Richters, 1900) [*Calohypsibius scabrosus* Thulin, 1928]

Haplohexapodibius Pilato & Beasley, 1987

Haplohexapodibius seductor Pilato & Beasley, 1987 [*Hexapodibius beasleyi* Maucci, 1988]

Haplomacrobotus May, 1948

Haplomacrobotus hermosillensis May, 1948

Haplomacrobotus utahensis Pilato & Beasley, 2005

Hexapodibius Pilato, 1969

Hexapodibius bindae Pilato, 1982

Hexapodibius boothi Dastych & McInnes, 1994

Hexapodibius christenberryae Pilato & Binda, 2003

Hexapodibius micronyx Pilato, 1969

Hexapodibius pseudomicronyx Robotti, 1972

Hexapodibius reginae Vargha, 1995

Parhexapodibius Pilato, 1969

Parhexapodibius bactrianus Biserov, 1999

Parhexapodibius castrii (Ramazzotti, 1964)

Parhexapodibius lagrecai (Binda & Pilato, 1969)

Parhexapodibius pilatoi (Bernard, 1977)

Parhexapodibius ramazzottii Manicardi & Bertolani, 1987

Hypsibiidae Pilato, 1969

Hypsibiinae Pilato, 1969

Acutuncus Pilato & Binda, 1997
Acutuncus antarcticus (Richters, 1904) [*Hypsibius simoizumii* Sudzuki, 1964]

Borealibius Pilato, Guidetti, Rebecchi, Lisi, Hansen & Bertolani, 2006
Borealibius zetlandicus (Murray, 1907)

Doryphoribius Pilato, 1969
Doryphoribius bertolanii Beasley & Pilato, 1987
Doryphoribius dawkinsi Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2010
Doryphoribius doryphorus (Binda & Pilato, 1969)
Doryphoribius dupliglobulatus Ito, 1995
Doryphoribius evelinae (Marcus, 1928)
Doryphoribius flavus (Iharos, 1966) [*Doryphoribius citrinus* (Maucci, 1973)]
Doryphoribius gibber Beasley & Pilato, 1987
Doryphoribius huangguoshuensis H. Wang, L. Wang & X. Li, 2007
Doryphoribius koreanus Moon, Kim & Bertolani, 1994
Doryphoribius korganovae Biserov, 1994
Doryphoribius longistipes Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2008
Doryphoribius macrodon Binda, Pilato & Dastyk, 1980
Doryphoribius maranguensis Binda & Pilato, 1995
Doryphoribius mariae Pilato & Binda, 1990
Doryphoribius mexicanus Beasley, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2008
Doryphoribius minimus Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2008
Doryphoribius neglectus Pilato & Lisi, 2004
Doryphoribius picoensis Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2008
Doryphoribius pilatoi R. Bertolani, 1984
Doryphoribius polynettae Biserov, 1988
Doryphoribius qinlingense X. Li, Su & Yu, 2004
Doryphoribius quadrituberculatus Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004
Doryphoribius smokiensis Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2007
Doryphoribius taiwanus X. Li & H. Li, 2008
Doryphoribius tergumrudis Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2008
Doryphoribius turkmenicus Biserov, 1999
Doryphoribius vietnamensis (Iharos, 1969)
Doryphoribius zappalai Pilato, 1971
Doryphoribius zyxiglobus (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978)

Eremobiotus Biserov, 1992
Eremobiotus alicatai (Binda, 1969)
Eremobiotus ovezovae Biserov, 1992

Halobiotus Kristensen, 1982
Halobiotus arcturulus Crisp & Kristensen, 1983
Halobiotus crispae Kristensen, 1982
Halobiotus stenostomus (Richters, 1908) [*Macrobiotus appelloefi* Richters, 1908; *Hypsibius* (*Isohypsibius*) *geddesi* Hallas, 1971]

Hypsibius Ehrenberg, 1848

Hypsibius allisoni Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978
Hypsibius antonovae (Biserov, 1990)
Hypsibius arcticus (Murray, 1907) [*Macrobotus heinisi* Richters, 1907]
Hypsibius biscuitiformis Bartoš, 1960
Hypsibius calcaratus Bartoš, 1935
Hypsibius camelopardalis Ramazzotti & Maucci, 1983
Hypsibius choucoutiensis Rahm, 1937
Hypsibius conifer Mihelčič, 1938
Hypsibius convergens (Urbanowicz, 1925)
Hypsibius dujardini (Doyère, 1840) [*Macrobotus palustris* Dujardin, 1851; *Macrobotus lacustris* Dujardin, 1851; *Macrobotus tetradactylus* Lance, 1896; *Macrobotus murrayi* Richters, 1907; *Macrobotus samoanus* Richters, 1908; *Macrobotus breckneri* Richters, 1910; *Macrobotus ursellus* Della Valle, 1915; *Hypsibius murrayi* Marcus, 1929]
Hypsibius fuhrmanni (Heinis, 1914)
Hypsibius giusepperamazotti Sudzuki, 1975
Hypsibius heardensis Miller, McInnes & Bergstrom, 2005
Hypsibius hypostomus Bartoš, 1935
Hypsibius iskandarovi Tumanov, 1997
Hypsibius janetscheki Ramazzotti, 1968
Hypsibius klebelsbergi Mihelčič, 1959
Hypsibius kunmingensis Yang, 2002
Hypsibius macrocalcaratus Beasley, 1988
Hypsibius maculatus Iharos, 1969
Hypsibius marcelli Pilato, 1990
Hypsibius microps Thulin, 1928 <Amended by Kaczmarek & Michalczyk 2009>
Hypsibius montanus Iharos, 1940 [*Hypsibius iharosi* Bartoš, 1941]
Hypsibius morikawai Ito, 1995
Hypsibius multituberculatus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2003
Hypsibius novaezeelandiae Pilato & Binda, 1997
Hypsibius pachyunguis Maucci, 1996
Hypsibius pallidus Thulin, 1911 <Amended by Kaczmarek & Michalczyk 2009>
Hypsibius pedrottii Bertolani, Manicardi & Gibertoni, 1987
Hypsibius pradellii Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1996
Hypsibius ragonesei Binda & Pilato, 1985
Hypsibius roanensis Nelson & McGlothlin, 1993
Hypsibius runae Bartoš, 1941
Hypsibius scaber Maucci, 1987
Hypsibius scabropygus Cuénot, 1929
Hypsibius septulatus Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2004
Hypsibius seychellensis Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006
***Hypsibius shaanxiensis* H. Li & X. Li, 2008**
Hypsibius stiliferus Abe, 2004
Hypsibius thaleri Dastych, 2004

Isohypsibius Thulin, 1928

Isohypsibius altai Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2006
Isohypsibius annulatus annulatus (Murray, 1905)
Isohypsibius annulatus minor (Ramazzotti, 1945)
Isohypsibius arbiter Binda, 1980
Isohypsibius archangajensis Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004
Isohypsibius arcuatus (Bartoš, 1934)
Isohypsibius asper (Murray, 1906)
Isohypsibius austriacus (Iharos, 1966)
Isohypsibius baicalensis (Ramazzotti, 1966)
Isohypsibius baldii (Ramazzotti, 1945)
Isohypsibius baldioides Tumanov, 2003
Isohypsibius barbarae Pilato & Binda, 2002
Isohypsibius bartosi (Iharos, 1966)
Isohypsibius basalovoi (Durante & Maucci, 1973)
Isohypsibius belliformis (Mihelčič, 1971)
Isohypsibius bellus (Mihelčič, 1971)
Isohypsibius borkini Tumanov, 2003
Isohypsibius brevispinosus (Iharos, 1966)
Isohypsibius brevitubulatus Rho, Chang & Kim, 1997
Isohypsibius brulloi Pilato & Pennisi, 1976
Isohypsibius bulbifer (Mihelčič, 1957)
Isohypsibius cameruni (Iharos, 1969)
Isohypsibius campbellensis Pilato, 1996
Isohypsibius canadensis (Murray, 1910)
Isohypsibius ceciliae Pilato & Binda, 1987
Isohypsibius changbaiensis Yang, 1999
Isohypsibius chiarae Maucci, 1987 [*Isohypsibius bertolanii* Manicardi, 1989]
Isohypsibius costatus (Mihelčič, 1971)
Isohypsibius cyrilli (Mihelčič, 1951)
Isohypsibius damxungensis Yang, 2007
Isohypsibius dastychi Pilato, Bertolani & Binda, 1982
Isohypsibius deconincki Pilato, 1971
Isohypsibius deflexus (Mihelčič, 1960)
Isohypsibius dudichi (Iharos, 1964)
Isohypsibius durantee (Maucci, 1978)
Isohypsibius effusus (Mihelčič, 1971)
Isohypsibius elegans Binda & Pilato, 1971
Isohypsibius eplenyiensis (Iharos, 1970)
Isohypsibius franzi (Mihelčič, 1951)
Isohypsibius fuscus (Mihelčič, 1971/72)
Isohypsibius gilvus Biserov, 1986
Isohypsibius glaber (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1979)
Isohypsibius glazovi Biserov, 1999
Isohypsibius gracilis (Iharos, 1966)
Isohypsibius granditintinus Chang & Rho, 1996
Isohypsibius granulifer granulifer Thulin, 1928
Isohypsibius granulifer koreanensis (Iharos, 1971)

Isohypsibius gyulai (Mihelčič, 1971)
Isohypsibius hadzii (Mihelčič, 1938)
Isohypsibius helenae (Iharos, 1964)
Isohypsibius hydrogogianus Ito & Tagami, 1993
Isohypsibius hypostomoides (Mihelčič, 1971)
Isohypsibius improvisus Dastych, 1984
Isohypsibius indicus (Murray, 1907)
Isohypsibius irregibilis Biserov, 1992
Isohypsibius jakieli Dastych, 1984
Isohypsibius jingshanensis Yang, 2003
Isohypsibius jinhouensis Yang, 2007
Isohypsibius josephi (Iharos, 1964)
Isohypsibius kenodontis Kendall-Fite & Nelson, 1996
Isohypsibius kotovae Tumanov, 2003
Isohypsibius kristenseni Pilato, Catanzaro & Binda, 1989
Isohypsibius ladogensis Tumanov, 2003
Isohypsibius laevis McInnes, 1995
Isohypsibius latiunguis (Iharos, 1964)
Isohypsibius leithaicus (Iharos, 1966)
Isohypsibius liae X. Li & L. Wang, 2006
Isohypsibius lineatus (Mihelčič, 1969)
Isohypsibius longiunguis Pilato, 1974
Isohypsibius lunulatus (Iharos, 1966)
Isohypsibius macrodactylus (Maucci, 1978) [*Isohypsibius zierhofferi* Dastych, 1980]
Isohypsibius malawiensis Jørgensen, 2001
Isohypsibius mammillosus (Iharos, 1964)
Isohypsibius marcellinoi Binda & Pilato, 1971
Isohypsibius marii R. Bertolani, 1982
Isohypsibius mihelcici (Iharos, 1964)
Isohypsibius monoicus R. Bertolani, 1982
Isohypsibius monstruosus Maucci, 1991
Isohypsibius montanus Mihelčič, 1938
Isohypsibius myrops (du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944)
Isohypsibius neoundulatus (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975)
Isohypsibius nipponicus Sudzuki, 1975
Isohypsibius nodosus (Murray, 1907)
Isohypsibius novaeguineae (Iharos, 1967)
Isohypsibius palmai Pilato, 1996
Isohypsibius panovi Tumanov, 2005
Isohypsibius papillifer papillifer (Murray, 1905)
Isohypsibius papillifer bulbosus (Marcus, 1928)
Isohypsibius papillifer indicus (Iharos, 1969)
Isohypsibius pappi (Iharos, 1966)
Isohypsibius pauper (Mihelčič, 1971)
Isohypsibius pilatoi (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1979)
Isohypsibius pratensis (Iharos, 1964)
Isohypsibius prosostomus prosostomus Thulin, 1928

Isohypsibius prosostomus cambrensis (Morgan, 1976)
Isohypsibius pseudoundulatus (da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1964)
Isohypsibius pulcher (Mihelčič, 1971/72)
Isohypsibius pushkini Tumanov, 2003
Isohypsibius qinlingensis X. Li, L. Wang & Yu, 2005
Isohypsibius rahmi X. Li & L. Wang, 2006
Isohypsibius reticulatus Pilato, 1973
Isohypsibius roberti Biserov, 1996
Isohypsibius ronsisvallei Binda & Pilato, 1969
Isohypsibius rudescui (Iharos, 1966)
Isohypsibius rugosus Guidi & Grabowski, 1996
Isohypsibius sabellai Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2004
Isohypsibius sattleri (Richters, 1902) [*Hypsibius bakonyiensis* Iharos, 1964] {the correct reference of Dastych 1990 cited in the previous check lists is: Dastych, H. (1991) *Isohypsibius sattleri* (Richters 1902), a valid species (Tardigrada). *Senckenbergiana biologica*, 71, 181–189.}
Isohypsibius schaudinni (Richters, 1909)
Isohypsibius sculptus (Ramazzotti, 1962)
Isohypsibius sellnicki (Mihelčič, 1962)
Isohypsibius septentrionalis Thulin, 1928
Isohypsibius silvicola (Iharos, 1966)
Isohypsibius sismicus (Maucci, 1978)
Isohypsibius solidus (Mihelčič, 1971)
Isohypsibius taibaiensis X. Li & L. Wang, 2005
Isohypsibius tetradactyloides (Richters, 1907)
Isohypsibius theresiae (Iharos, 1964)
Isohypsibius torulosus (Mihelčič, 1959)
Isohypsibius truncorum (Iharos, 1964)
Isohypsibius tuberculatus (Plate, 1888)
Isohypsibius tuberculoides (Mihelčič, 1951)
Isohypsibius tubereticulatus Pilato & Catanzaro, 1989
Isohypsibius tucumanensis Claps & Rossi, 1984
Isohypsibius undulatus Thulin, 1928
Isohypsibius vej dovskyi (Bartoš, 1939)
Isohypsibius verae Pilato & Catanzaro, 1989
Isohypsibius verrucosus (Della Valle, 1915) [*Isohypsibius gibbus* (Marcus, 1928)]
Isohypsibius wilsoni (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978)
Isohypsibius woodsae Kathman, 1990
Isohypsibius yunnanensis Yang, 2002

Mixibius Pilato, 1992

Mixibius fueginus Pilato & Binda, 1996
Mixibius ninguidus Biserov, 1999
Mixibius ornatus Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2002
Mixibius pilatoi L. Wang, 2009
Mixibius saracenus (Pilato, 1973)
Mixibius sutirae Pilato, Binda & Lisi 2004

Mixibius tibetanus H.Li & X.Li, 2008

Pseudobiotus Nelson, 1980

Pseudobiotus kathmanae Nelson, Marley & Bertolani, 1999

Pseudobiotus longiunguis (Iharos, 1968)

Pseudobiotus matici (Pilato, 1971)

Pseudobiotus megalonyx (Thulin, 1928)

Pseudobiotus spinifer Chang, Kaczmarek, Lee & Michalczyk, 2007

Pseudobiotus vladimiri Biserov, Dudichev & Biserova, 2001 <Amended by Chang *et al.* 2007>

Ramajendas Pilato & Binda, 1990

Ramajendas frigidus Pilato & Binda, 1990

Ramajendas heatwolei Miller, Horning & Dastych, 1995

Ramajendas renaudi (Ramazzotti, 1972)

Ramazottius Binda & Pilato, 1986

Ramazottius affinis Bertolani, Guidetti & Rebecchi, 1994

Ramazottius andreevi Biserov, 1997/98

Ramazottius anomalus (Ramazzotti, 1962)

Ramazottius baumanni (Ramazzotti, 1962)

Ramazottius bunikowskiae Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Diduszko, 2006

Ramazottius cataphractus (Maucci, 1974)

Ramazottius caucasicus Biserov, 1997/98

Ramazottius edmondabouti Séméria, 1993

Ramazottius horningi Binda & Pilato, 1994

Ramazottius ljudmilae Biserov, 1997/98

Ramazottius montivagus (Dastych, 1983)

Ramazottius nivalis Dastych, 2006

Ramazottius novemcinctus (Marcus, 1936)

Ramazottius oberhaeuseri (Doyère, 1840)

Ramazottius rupeus Biserov, 1999

Ramazottius saltensis (Claps & Rossi, 1984)

Ramazottius semisculptus Pilato & Rebecchi, 1992

Ramazottius subanomalus (Biserov, 1985)

Ramazottius szeptycki (Dastych, 1980) <Amended by Dastych 2009>

Ramazottius theroni Dastych, 1993

Ramazottius thulini (Pilato, 1970)

Ramazottius tribulosus Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1988

Ramazottius valaamis Biserov & Tumanov, 1993

Ramazottius varieornatus Bertolani & Kinchin, 1993

Thalerius Dastych, 2009

Thalerius konradi Dastych, 2009

Thulinus R. Bertolani, 2003

[*Thulinia* R. Bertolani, 1982]

Thulinus augusti (Murray, 1907) [*Macrobotus lacustris* Wenck, 1914]
Thulinus itoi (Tsurusaki, 1980)
Thulinus ruffoi (R. Bertolani, 1982)
Thulinus saltursus (Schuster, Toftner & Grigarick, 1978) <Amended and transferred from
Isohypsibius to *Thulinus* by Kaczmarek et al. 2010>
Thulinus stephaniae (Pilato, 1974)

Diphasconinae Dastych, 1992

Diphascon (*Diphascon*) Plate, 1888

Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *aculeatum* (Maucci, 1951-1952)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *alpinum* Murray, 1906
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *australianum* Pilato & Binda, 1998
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *bidropion* Ito, 1995
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *birklehofi* Rolf Schuster, 1999
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *bisbullatum* (Iharos, 1964)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *boreale* Biserov, 1996
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *brevipes* (Marcus, 1936)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *bullatum* Murray, 1905
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *burti* Nelson, 1991
Diphascon* (*Diphascon*) *chilenense Plate, 1888
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *claxtonae* Pilato & Binda, 1998
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *dastychi* Pilato & Binda, 1999
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *dolomiticum* Pilato & Bertolani, 2005
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *elongatum* (Mihelčič, 1959)
Diphascon* (*Diphascon*) *faialense Fontoura & Pilato, 2007
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *gerdae* (Mihelčič, 1951)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *granifer* Greven, 1972
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *halapiense* (Iharos, 1964)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *higginsi* Binda, 1971
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *humicus* Bertolani, Guidetti & Rebecchi, 1995
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *hydrophilum* Pilato, Binda, Bertolani & Lisi, 2005
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *iharosi* Vargha, 1995
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *iltisi* (Schuster & Grigarick, 1965)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *langhovdense* (Sudzuki, 1964)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *latipes* (Mihelčič, 1955)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *mirabilis* Dastych, 1984
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *mitrense* Pilato, Binda & Qualtieri, 1999
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *nelsonae* Pilato, Binda, Bertolani & Lisi, 2005
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *nobilei* (Binda, 1969)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *nodulosum* (Ramazzotti, 1957)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *nonbullatum* (Mihelčič, 1951)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *oculatum oculatum* Murray, 1906
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *oculatum alpinum* (Mihelčič, 1964)
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *oculatum canadense* Murray, 1910 [*Hypsibius vancouverensis* Thulin,
1911]
Diphascon (*Diphascon*) *ongulense* (Morikawa, 1962)

Diphascon (Diphascon) opisthoglyptum Maucci, 1987
Diphascon (Diphascon) patanei Binda & Pilato, 1971
Diphascon (Diphascon) pingue pingue (Marcus, 1936)
Diphascon (Diphascon) pingue brunsvicense Argue, 1972
Diphascon (Diphascon) pinguiforme Pilato & Binda, 1997/98
Diphascon (Diphascon) platyungue Pilato, Binda, Bertolani & Lisi, 2005
Diphascon (Diphascon) polare Pilato & Binda, 1999
Diphascon (Diphascon) puniceum (Jennings, 1976)
Diphascon (Diphascon) ramazzottii (Robotti, 1970)
Diphascon (Diphascon) recamieri Richters, 1911
Diphascon (Diphascon) rugocaudatum (Rodriguez Roda, 1952)
Diphascon (Diphascon) rugosum (Bartoš, 1935)
Diphascon (Diphascon) sanae Dastych, Ryan & Watkins, 1990
Diphascon (Diphascon) secchii Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1996
Diphascon (Diphascon) serratum Pilato, Binda, Bertolani & Lisi, 2005
Diphascon (Diphascon) sexbullatum Ito, 1995
Diphascon (Diphascon) stappersi Richters, 1911
Diphascon (Diphascon) tenue Thulin, 1928
Diphascon (Diphascon) trachydorsatum (Bartoš, 1937)
Diphascon (Diphascon) victoriae Pilato & Binda, 1999
Diphascon (Diphascon) zaniewi Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004

Diphascon (Adropion) Pilato, 1987

Diphascon (Adropion) arduifrons Thulin, 1928
Diphascon (Adropion) behanae Dastych, 1987
Diphascon (Adropion) belgicae Richters, 1911 [*Fujiscon diphasconiellum* Ito, 1991]
Diphascon (Adropion) carolae Binda & Pilato, 1969
Diphascon (Adropion) clavatum (Bartoš, 1935)
Diphascon (Adropion) gordonense Pilato, Claxton & Horning, 1991
Diphascon (Adropion) greveni Dastych, 1984
Diphascon (Adropion) linzhiensis X. Li, 2007
Diphascon (Adropion) mauccii Dastych & McInnes, 1996
Diphascon (Adropion) modestum Binda, Pilato & Dastych, 1984
Diphascon (Adropion) montigenum Pilato & Dastych, 1974
Diphascon (Adropion) onorei Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2002
Diphascon (Adropion) prorsirostre Thulin, 1928
Diphascon (Adropion) scoticum scoticum Murray, 1905 [*Diphascon crozetense* Richters, 1907]
Diphascon (Adropion) scoticum ommatophorum (Thulin, 1911)
Diphascon (Adropion) scoticum qinlingensis X. Li & Liu, 2005
Diphascon (Adropion) tricuspdatum Binda & Pilato, 2000
Diphascon (Adropion) triodon (Maucci, 1996)

Diphascon bicorne (Mihelčič, 1971)
Diphascon coniferens (Bartoš, 1960)
Diphascon marcuzzii (Mihelčič, 1971)
Diphascon mariae (Mihelčič, 1951)
Diphascon punctatum (Iharos, 1962)

Diphascon rivulare (Mihelčič, 1967)
Diphascon speciosum (Mihelčič, 1971)

Bindius Pilato, 2009

***Bindius triquetrus* Pilato, 2009**

Hebesuncus Pilato, 1987

Hebesuncus conjungens (Thulin, 1911)
Hebesuncus ryani Dastych & Harris, 1994
Hebesuncus schusteri (Dastych, 1984)

Paradiphascon Dastych, 1992

Paradiphascon manningi Dastych, 1992

Itaquasconinae Rudescu, 1964

Astatumen Pilato, 1997

Astatumen bartosi (Węglarska, 1959)
Astatumen tamaensis (Sudzuki, 1975)
Astatumen tamurai (Ito, 1990)
Astatumen trinacriae (Arcidiacono, 1962) [*Itaquascon ramazzottii* Iharos, 1966]

Itaquascon de Barros, 1939

Itaquascon biserovi Pilato, Binda & Moncada, 1999
Itaquascon cambewarrense Pilato, Binda & Claxton, 2002
Itaquascon enckelli (Mihelčič, 1971/72)
Itaquascon globuliferum Abe & Ito, 1994
Itaquascon mongolicus Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Węglarska, 2002
Itaquascon pawlowskii Węglarska, 1973
***Itaquascon pisoniae* Pilato & Lisi, 2009**
Itaquascon placophorum Maucci, 1973
Itaquascon simplex (Mihelčič, 1971)
Itaquascon umbellinae de Barros, 1939
Itaquascon unguiculum Pilato, Binda & Claxton, 2002

Mesocrista Pilato, 1987

Mesocrista marcusii (Rudescu, 1964)
Mesocrista spitzbergensis (Richters, 1903)

Parascon Pilato & Binda, 1987

Parascon nichollsae Pilato & Lisi, 2004
Parascon schusteri Pilato & Binda, 1987

Platicrista Pilato, 1987

Platicrista affine (Mihelčič, 1951)
Platicrista angustata (Murray, 1905)
Platicrista cheleusis Kathman, 1990 [*Diphascon craigi* Beasley, 1990]

Platicrista horribilis Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2003
Platicrista itaquasconoide (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975)
Platicrista ramsayi Marley, 2006

Macrobiotidae Thulin, 1928

Adorybiotus Maucci & Ramazzotti, 1981
Adorybiotus granulatus (Richters, 1903)

Biserovus Guidetti & Pilato, 2003
Biserovus bindae (Christenberry & Higgins, 1979)

Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) Dastych, 1993
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) digeronimoi Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) filmeri Dastych, 1993
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) gildae (Maucci & Durante Pasa, 1980)
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) hainanensis X. Li, D. Wang & L. Wang, 2008
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) imperialis Abe & Takeda, 2000
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) longinoi Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Guidetti, 2006
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) occultus Dastych, 1993
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) parvicalcar Pilato & Lisi, 2009

Calcarobiotus (Discrepunguis) Guidetti & Bertolani, 2001
Calcarobiotus (Discrepunguis) polygonatus (Binda & Guglielmino, 1991) [*Macrobiotus eugranulatus* Maucci, 1993]
Calcarobiotus (Discrepunguis) tetrannulatus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004

Famelobiotus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004
Famelobiotus scalicii Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004

Insuetifurca Guidetti & Pilato, 2003
Insuetifurca arrowsmithi (Kathman & Nelson, 1989)
Insuetifurca austronipponica Abe, 2005
Insuetifurca fujiense (Ito, 1997)
Insuetifurca xiae (X. Li, Su & Yu, 2004) <Amended and transferred from *Biserovus* to *Insuetifurca* by Li 2009>

Macrobiotus C.A.S. Schultze, 1834
Macrobiotus almadai Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2008
Macrobiotus altitudinalis Biserov, 1997/98
Macrobiotus alvaroi Pilato & Kaczmarek, 2007
Macrobiotus anderssoni Richters, 1907
Macrobiotus andinus Maucci, 1988
Macrobiotus annae Richters, 1908
Macrobiotus aradasi Binda, Pilato & Lisi, 2005
Macrobiotus arguei Pilato & Sperlinga, 1975
Macrobiotus ariekammensis Węglarska, 1965 [*Macrobiotus adelges* Dastych, 1977]

Macrobotus armatus Pilato & Binda, 1996
Macrobotus artipharyngis Iharos, 1940
Macrobotus ascensionis Richters, 1908
Macrobotus australis Pilato & D'Urso, 1976
Macrobotus baltatus McInnes, 1991
Macrobotus barabanovi Tumanov, 2005
Macrobotus barbarae Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Degma, 2007
Macrobotus biserovi Bertolani, Guidi & Rebecchi, 1996
Macrobotus blocki Dastych, 1984
Macrobotus bondavallii Manicardi, 1989
Macrobotus brevipes Mihelčič, 1971/72
Macrobotus caelicola Kathman, 1990
Macrobotus carsicus Maucci, 1954
Macrobotus ciprianoi Guil, Guidetti & Machordom, 2007
Macrobotus contii Pilato & Lisi, 2006
Macrobotus coronatus de Barros, 1942
Macrobotus creber Pilato & Lisi, 2009
Macrobotus crenulatus Richters, 1904 [*Macrobotus dentatus* Binda, 1974]
Macrobotus danielisae Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006
Macrobotus danilovi Tumanov, 2007
Macrobotus dariae Pilato & Bertolani, 2004
Macrobotus denticulus Dastych, 2002
Macrobotus diffusus Binda & Pilato, 1987
Macrobotus diguensis Pilato & Lisi, 2009
Macrobotus divergens Binda, Pilato & Lisi, 2005
Macrobotus diversus Biserov, 1990
Macrobotus drakensbergi Dastych, 1993
Macrobotus echinogenitus Richters, 1904
Macrobotus erminiae Binda & Pilato, 1999
Macrobotus evelinae de Barros, 1938
Macrobotus furciger Murray, 1907 [*Macrobotus ehrenbergi* Heinis, 1921; *Macrobotus furcatus* Murray, 1906}
Macrobotus gemmatus Bartoš, 1963
Macrobotus glebkai Biserov, 1990
Macrobotus grandis Richters, 1911
Macrobotus halei Bartels, Pilato, Lisi & Nelson, 2009
Macrobotus hapukuensis Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006
Macrobotus harmsworthi harmsworthi Murray, 1907
Macrobotus harmsworthi obscurus Dastych, 1985
Macrobotus hibiscus de Barros, 1942
Macrobotus hieronimi Pilato & Claxton, 1988
Macrobotus higginsi Maucci, 1987
Macrobotus hufelandi hufelandi C.A.S. Schultze, 1833
Macrobotus hufelandi maculatus Iharos, 1973
Macrobotus humilis Binda & Pilato, 2001
Macrobotus hyperboreus Biserov, 1990
Macrobotus hyperonyx Maucci, 1983

Macrobotus hystricogenitus Maucci, 1978
Macrobotus iharosi Pilato, Binda & Catanzaro, 1991
Macrobotus insignis Bartoš, 1963
Macrobotus insularis Pilato, 2006
Macrobotus islandicus islandicus Richters, 1904 [*Macrobotus ruffoi* Maucci, 1973]
Macrobotus islandicus nicaraguensis Séméria, 1985
Macrobotus joannae Pilato & Binda, 1983
Macrobotus kazmierskii Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2009
Macrobotus kirghizicus Tumanov, 2005
Macrobotus kolleri Mihelčič, 1951
Macrobotus komareki Bartoš, 1939
Macrobotus kovalevi Tumanov, 2004
Macrobotus kozharai Biserov, 1999
Macrobotus krynauwi Dastych & Harris, 1995
Macrobotus kurasi Dastych, 1981
Macrobotus lazzaroi Maucci, 1986 [*Macrobotus spallanzanii* Maucci, 1973]
Macrobotus lissostomus Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1979
Macrobotus liviae Ramazzotti, 1962
Macrobotus longipes Mihelčič, 1971/72
Macrobotus lusitanicus Maucci & Durante Pasa, 1984
Macrobotus macrocalix Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1993
Macrobotus madegassus Maucci, 1993
Macrobotus mandalae Pilato, 1974
Macrobotus marlenae Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004
Macrobotus martini Bartels, Pilato, Lisi & Nelson, 2009
Macrobotus mauccii Pilato, 1974
Macrobotus meridionalis Richters, 1909
Macrobotus modestus Pilato & Lisi, 2009
Macrobotus mongolicus Maucci, 1988
Macrobotus montanus Murray, 1910 [*Macrobotus morulatus* Bartoš, 1936]
Macrobotus mottai Binda & Pilato, 1994
Macrobotus nelsonae Guidetti, 1998
Macrobotus neuquensis Rossi, Claps & Ardohain, 2009
Macrobotus norvegicus Mihelčič, 1971/72
Macrobotus nuragicus Pilato & Sperlinga, 1975
Macrobotus occidentalis occidentalis Murray, 1910
Macrobotus occidentalis striatus Dastych, 1974
Macrobotus ocotensis Pilato, 2006
Macrobotus orcadensis Murray, 1907
Macrobotus ovidii Bartoš, 1937
Macrobotus ovostriatus Pilato & Patanè, 1998
Macrobotus ovovillosus Baumann, 1960
Macrobotus pallarii Maucci, 1954 [*Macrobotus aviglianae* Robotti, 1970]
Macrobotus papillosus Iharos, 1963
Macrobotus patagonicus Maucci, 1988
Macrobotus patiens Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2000
Macrobotus perfidus Pilato & Lisi, 2009

Macrobotus persimilis Binda & Pilato, 1972
Macrobotus personatus Biserov, 1990
Macrobotus peterseni Maucci, 1991
Macrobotus pilatoi Binda & Rebecchi, 1992
Macrobotus polaris Murray, 1910
Macrobotus polonicus Pilato, Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Lisi, 2003
Macrobotus polyopus Marcus, 1928
Macrobotus porteri Rahm, 1931
Macrobotus potockii Węglarska, 1968
Macrobotus primitivae de Barros, 1942
Macrobotus privitera Binda, Pilato, Moncada & Napolitano, 2001
Macrobotus psephus du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944
Macrobotus pseudocoronatus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006
Macrobotus pseudofurcatus Pilato, 1972
Macrobotus pseudoliviae Pilato & Binda, 1996
Macrobotus pseudonuragicus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004
Macrobotus punctillus Pilato, Binda & Azzaro, 1990
Macrobotus radiatus Pilato, Binda & Catanzaro, 1991
Macrobotus ragonesei Binda, Pilato, Moncada & Napolitano, 2001
Macrobotus ramoli Dastyh, 2005
Macrobotus rawsoni Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978
Macrobotus recens Cuénot, 1932
Macrobotus reinhardti Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2003
Macrobotus rigidus Pilato & Lisi, 2006
Macrobotus rollei Heinis, 1921
Macrobotus rubens Murray, 1907
Macrobotus sandrae Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1993
Macrobotus santoroi Pilato & D'Urso, 1976
Macrobotus sapiens Binda & Pilato, 1984
Macrobotus semmelweisi Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006
Macrobotus serratus Bertolani, Guidi & Rebecchi, 1996
Macrobotus seychellensis Biserov, 1994
Macrobotus shennongensis Yang, 1999
Macrobotus siamensis Tumanov, 2006
Macrobotus sicheli Binda, Pilato & Lisi, 2005
Macrobotus simulans Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2000
Macrobotus sklodowskae Michalczyk, Kaczmarek & Węglarska, 2006
Macrobotus snaresensis Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978
Macrobotus spectabilis Thulin, 1928
Macrobotus spertii Ramazzotti, 1957
Macrobotus stellaris du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944
Macrobotus striatus Mihelčič, 1949
Macrobotus submorulatus Iharos, 1966
Macrobotus szeptyckii Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2009
Macrobotus tehuelchensis Rossi, Claps & Ardohain, 2009
Macrobotus tenuiformis Tumanov, 2007
Macrobotus tenuis Binda & Pilato, 1972

Macrobotus terminalis Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1993
Macrobotus terricola Mihelčič, 1951
Macrobotus tetraplacoides Fontoura, 1981
Macrobotus topali Iharos, 1969
Macrobotus virgatus Murray, 1910
Macrobotus voronkovi Tumanov, 2007
Macrobotus wauensis Iharos, 1973
Macrobotus willardi Pilato, 1977
Macrobotus yunshanensis Yang, 2002

Minibiotus R.O. Schuster, 1980

Minibiotus acontistus (de Barros, 1942)
Minibiotus aculeatus (Murray, 1910) [*Macrobotus intermedius subjulietae* Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978]
Minibiotus africanus Binda & Pilato, 1995
Minibiotus allani (Murray, 1913)
Minibiotus aquatilis Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus asteris Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus bisoctus (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978)
Minibiotus claxtonae Rossi, Claps & Ardohain, 2009
Minibiotus constellatus Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2003
Minibiotus continuus Pilato & Lisi, 2006
Minibiotus crassidens (Murray, 1907)
Minibiotus decrescens Binda & Pilato, 1995
Minibiotus diphasconides (Iharos, 1969)
Minibiotus eichhorni Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2004
Minibiotus ethelae Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus fallax Pilato, Claxton & Binda, 1989
Minibiotus floriparus Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus furcatus (Ehrenberg, 1859) [*nec Macrobotus furcatus* Murray, 1906]
Minibiotus granatai (Pardi, 1941)
Minibiotus gumersindoi Guil & Guidetti, 2005
Minibiotus harrylewisi Meyer & Hinton, 2009
Minibiotus hispidus Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus hufelandioides (Murray, 1910)
Minibiotus intermedius (Plate, 1888)
Minibiotus julietae (de Barros, 1942)
Minibiotus keppelensis Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus maculartus Pilato & Claxton, 1988
Minibiotus marcusii (de Barros, 1942)
Minibiotus milleri Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus orthofasciatus Fontoura, Pilato, Lisi & Morais, 2009
Minibiotus pilatus Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus poricinctus Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus pustulatus (Ramazzotti, 1959)
Minibiotus ramazzottii Binda & Pilato, 1992
Minibiotus scopulus Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus sidereus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2003
Minibiotus stuckenbergi (Dastyh, Ryan & Watkins, 1990)
Minibiotus subintermedius (Ramazzotti, 1962)
Minibiotus taiti Claxton, 1998
Minibiotus vinciguerrae Binda & Pilato, 1992
Minibiotus weglarskae Michalczyk, Kaczmarek & Claxton, 2005
Minibiotus weinerorum (Dastyh, 1984)
Minibiotus wuzhishanensis X. Li, D. Wang & L. Wang, 2008
Minibiotus xavieri Fontoura, Pilato, Morais & Lisi, 2009

Minilentus Guidetti & Pilato, 2003

Minilentus dubius (Schuster & Toftner, 1982)

Paramacrobotus Guidetti, Schill, Bertolani, Dandekar & Wolf, 2009

Paramacrobotus alekseevi (Tumanov, 2005) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus areolatus (Murray, 1907) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus beotiae (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1979) {species dubia; Guidetti et al. 2009}
Paramacrobotus centesimus (Pilato, 2000) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus chieregoi (Maucci & Durante Pasa, 1980) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus corgatensis (Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2002) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus crenatus (Maucci, 1991) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus csotiensis (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus danielae (Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2001) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus derkai (Degma, Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2008) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus garynahi (Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Diduszko, 2005) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus gerlachae (Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus huziori (Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus lorenae (Biserov, 1996) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus magdalenae (Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus peteri (Pilato, Claxton & Binda, 1989) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>
Paramacrobotus richtersi (Murray, 1911) [*Macrobotus schultzei* Greeff, 1866] <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti et al. 2009>

Paramacrobotus rioplatensis (Claps & Rossi, 1997) {doubly attributed to the genus; Guidetti *et al.* 2009}
Paramacrobotus savai (Binda and Pilato, 2001) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>
Paramacrobotus tonollii (Ramazzotti, 1956) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>
Paramacrobotus vanescens (Pilato, Binda and Catanzaro, 1991) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>
Paramacrobotus walteri (Biserov, 1997/98) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* to *Paramacrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Pseudodiphascon Ramazzotti, 1965

Pseudodiphascon inflexum (Arcidiacono, 1964)

Pseudohexapodibius Bertolani & Biserov, 1996

Pseudohexapodibius degenerans (Biserov, 1990)

Richtersius Pilato & Binda, 1989

[*Richtersia* Pilato & Binda, 1987]

Richtersius coronifer (Richters, 1903)

Schusterius Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2006

Schusterius tridigitus (R.O. Schuster, 1983)

Xerobiotus Bertolani & Biserov, 1996

Xerobiotus pseudohufelandi (Iharos, 1966) [*Macrobotus inermis* Binda & Pilato, 1971]

Xerobiotus xerophilus (Dastyk, 1978)

Murrayidae Guidetti, Gandolfi, Rossi & Bertolani, 2005

Dactylobiotus R.O. Schuster, 1980

Dactylobiotus ambiguus (Murray, 1907)

Dactylobiotus ampullaceus (Thulin, 1911)

Dactylobiotus aquatilis Yang, 1999

Dactylobiotus caldarellai Pilato & Binda, 1994

Dactylobiotus dervizi Biserov, 1998

Dactylobiotus dispar (Murray, 1907)

Dactylobiotus grandipes (Schuster, Toftner & Grigarick, 1978) <Amended by Kaczmarek & Michalczyk 2010>

Dactylobiotus haplonyx Maucci, 1981

Dactylobiotus henanensis Yang, 2002

Dactylobiotus kansae Beasley, Miller & Shively, 2009

Dactylobiotus lombardoi Binda & Pilato, 1999

Dactylobiotus luci Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Eggermont, 2008

Dactylobiotus macronyx (Dujardin, 1851)

Dactylobiotus octavi Guidetti, Altiero & Hansen, 2006

Dactylobiotus parthenogeneticus R. Bertolani, 1982

Dactylobiotus selenicus R. Bertolani, 1982

Macroversum Pilato & Catanzaro, 1988

Macroversum mirum Pilato & Catanzaro, 1988

Murrayon Bertolani & Pilato, 1988

Murrayon dianeae (Kristensen, 1982)

Murrayon hastatus (Murray, 1907)

Murrayon hibernicus (Murray, 1911)

Murrayon nocentinae (Ramazzotti, 1961)

Murrayon ovoglabellus (Biserov, 1988)

Murrayon pullari (Murray, 1907)

Murrayon stellatus Guidetti, 1998

Microhypsibiidae Pilato, 1998

Fractonotus Pilato, 1998

Fractonotus caelatus (Marcus, 1928)

Microhypsibius Thulin, 1928

Microhypsibius bertolanii Kristensen, 1982

Microhypsibius japonicus Ito, 1991

Microhypsibius minimus Kristensen, 1982

Microhypsibius truncatus Thulin, 1928

Necopinatidae Ramazzotti & Maucci, 1983

Necopinatum Pilato, 1971

Necopinatum mirabile Pilato, 1971

incertae sedis

Apodibius Dastych, 1983

Apodibius confusus Dastych, 1983

Apodibius nuntius Binda, 1984 [*Apodibius serventyi* Morgan & Nicholls, 1986]

Apodibius richardi Vargha, 1995

References

- Chang, C.Y., Kaczmarek, Ł., Lee, J.M. & Michalczyk, Ł. (2007) *Pseudobiotus spinifer*, a new tardigrade species (Eutardigrada: Hysibiidae) from Nakdong River, South Korea, with a redescription of *P. vladimiri* Biserov, Dudichev & Biserova. *Zoological Science*, 24, 623–629.
- Christenberry, D. & Mason W.H. (1979) Redescription of *Echiniscus virginicus* Riggin (Tardigrada) with notes on life history, range, and geographic variation. *Journal of the Alabama Academy of Science*, 50, 47-61.
- Dastych, H. (2009) Notes on the African limno-terrestrial tardigrade *Ramazzottius szepteyki*

- (Dastych, 1980) (Tardigrada). *Entomologische Mitteilungen aus dem Zoologischen Museum Hamburg*, 15: 87–91.
- Guidetti, R., Schill, R.O., Bertolani, R., Dandekar, T. & Wolf, M. (2009) New molecular data for tardigrade phylogeny, with the erection of *Paramacrobotus* gen. n. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research* (doi: 10.1111/j.1439-0469.2009.00526.x).
- Kaczmarek, Ł. & Michalczyk, Ł. (2009) Redescription of *Hypsibius microps* Thulin, 1928 and *H. pallidus* Thulin, 1911 (Eutardigrada: Hypsibiidae) based on the type material from the Thulin collection. *Zootaxa*, 2275: 60–68.
- Kaczmarek, Ł. & Michalczyk, Ł. (2010) Redescription of *Dactylobiotus grandipes* (Schuster, Toftner & Grigarick, 1978), the type species for the genus *Dactylobiotus* (Tardigrada: Macrobiotidae). *Genus*, 21: 155–162.
- Kaczmarek, Ł., Bertolani R. & Michalczyk, Ł. (2010) *Thulinus saltursus* comb. nov.: a new systematic position from *Isohypsibius saltursus* Schuster, Toftner & Grigarick, 1978 (Eutardigrada: Hypsibiidae) and a key for the genus *Thulinus*. *Zootaxa*, 2483: 58–64.
- Li, X. (2009) Revision of *Biserovus xiae* Li, Su and Yu, 2004 (Tardigrada: Macrobiotidae). *Zootaxa*, 2076, 63–68.
- Miller, W.R. & Mehlen, R.H. (2007) Tardigrades of North America: re-description of *Echiniscus tamus* Mehlen, 1969 (Tardigrada: Heterotardigrada: Echiniscoidae: Echiniscidae). *Proceedings of the Biological Society of Washington*, 120(2), 184–188.
- Özdikmen, H. (2008) *Bertolanius* nom. nov., a replacement name for the genus *Amphibolus* Bertolani, 1981 (Tardigrada: Parachela) with type species designation. *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 3(1), 330–332.
- Pilato, G., Fontoura, P. & Lisi, O. (2008a) New description of *Echiniscus viridis* Murray, 1910 and remarks on the *viridis* group. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology*, 35, 85–92.
- Pilato, G., Fontoura, P., Lisi, O. & Beasley, C. (2008b) New description of *Echiniscus scabrospinus* Fontoura, 1982, and description of a new species of *Echiniscus* (Heterotardigrada) from China. *Zootaxa*, 1856, 41–54 and *Zootaxa*, 1931, 68.